

UVAH

*Screening new antivirals as an
alternative treatment against CMV
infection*

*Búsqueda de nuevos antivirales
como alternativa al tratamiento
actual frente a la infección por CMV*

Máster Universitario en Microbiología aplicada a la Salud Pública e
Investigación en Enfermedades Infecciosas

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ABSTRACT

Human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) infection is an important cause of morbidity and mortality in individuals with an immature or dysfunctional immune system. Since currently there is no vaccine available, the first line of treatment for HCMV infection is the use of highly effective antivirals that are also associated with toxic side effects and high cost. In this sense, there is great interest in the search and development of new therapeutic alternatives that can be used for the treatment of HCMV infection. The use of essential oil compounds (EOCs) as antimicrobial agents has been widely investigated and several groups have demonstrated that they have a wide spectrum antibacterial, antifungal and even antiviral activity. In addition, other studies have shown the improvement of the antimicrobial potential and the lower toxicity of these EOCs when they are functionalized on silica surfaces.

The main objective of this study was to test the antiviral activity of 3 EOCs against HCMV infection in ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells. The studied EOCs were thymol, eugenol and vanillin either free and immobilised on amorphous silica particles. Cytotoxicity and antiviral activity assays revealed the low toxicity and high antiviral effect against HCMV infection of all three compounds but especiall for vanillin both free and functionalized to silica particles. The analysis of the expression levels of the main genomic targets (UL54, UL97, UL56 and UL51) against the virus showed that free vanillin influences all four genes in ARPE-19 cells. However, in MRC-5 cells, the expression levels of two of the common therapeutic targets (UL54 and UL51) were not affected by the presence of vanillin. These preliminary results could indicate that these EOCS may offer a new therapeutic alternative for HCMV infection and may serve to solve the problem of cross-resistance caused by the currently used antivirals.

KEYWORDS: Cytomegalovirus; Vanillin; Eugenol; Thymol; antiviral; qPCR

RESUMEN

La infección por citomegalovirus humano (HCMV) es una causa importante de morbilidad y mortalidad en individuos con un sistema inmune inmaduro o disfuncional. Actualmente no se dispone de una vacuna por lo que la primera línea de tratamiento frente a la infección por HCMV se basa en el uso de antivirales que, aunque presentan una alta eficacia, están asociados a efectos adversos como toxicidad y un coste elevado. Por estos motivos existe un interés creciente en la búsqueda y el desarrollo de alternativas terapéuticas que puedan ser utilizadas para el tratamiento de la infección por HCMV. Algunos componentes de aceites esenciales (EOCs) han sido estudiados como agentes antimicrobianos y se ha descrito su actividad antimicrobiana, antifúngica, así como antiviral. Además, otros trabajos han puesto de manifiesto la mejora del potencial antimicrobiano y la menor toxicidad de estos EOCs cuando se funcionalizan en superficies de sílice.

Por todo ello, el objetivo principal de este estudio fue testar la actividad antiviral frente a la infección por HCMV de 3 aceites esenciales en células ARPE-19 y MRC-5. Los EOCs estudiados fueron timol, eugenol y vainillina tanto libres como inmovilizados sobre partículas de sílice amorfa. Los ensayos de citotoxicidad y actividad antiviral revelaron la baja toxicidad y el alto efecto antiviral de todos ellos, pero especialmente de la vainillina tanto libre como funcionalizada. El análisis de los niveles de expresión de las principales dianas genómicas (UL54, UL97, UL56 y UL51) frente al virus demostró que la vainillina libre influye sobre los cuatro genes analizados en las células ARPE-19. Sin embargo, en células MRC-5, los niveles de expresión de dos de las dianas terapéuticas más comunes (UL54 y UL51) no se vieron afectados. Estos resultados preliminares podrían indicar que los EOCs estudiados podrían ser una nueva alternativa terapéutica, que podría resolver el problema de la resistencia cruzada causada por los antivirales utilizados actualmente.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Citomegalovirus; Vainillina; Eugenol; Timol; antiviral; qPCR

INDEX

1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Cytomegalovirus incidence	1
1.2. Cytomegalovirus structure.....	1
1.3. Cytomegalovirus infection and disease	2
1.3.1. Cell cycle	2
1.3.2. Cell infection	3
1.4. Treatment of cytomegalovirus infection.....	3
1.5. Biological activity of essential oils.....	5
1.5.1. Eugenol	6
1.5.2. Thymol	6
1.5.3. Vanillin	7
1.6. Enhanced essential oils in surface of silica supports.....	7
2. OBJECTIVES	9
3. MATERIALS AND METHODS	10
3.1. Cells and virus	10
3.2. EOCs handling	10
3.2.1. Free EOCs.....	10
3.2.2. Silica particles functionalized with EOCs preparation.....	10
3.3. Cytotoxicity assay.....	11
3.4. Antiviral activity assay.....	12
3.5. Fluorescence microscopy analysis	13
3.6. RNA extraction and qPCR.....	13
4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	14
4.1. Cell toxicity and antimicrobial activity of the free EOCs	14
4.2. Cell toxicity and antiviral activity of the EOCs-functionalized and bare silica particles	17
4.3. Viral transcript expression analysis of the main antiviral genomic targets	21
5. CONCLUSIONS	24
6. REFERENCES	25
7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	30
8. APPENDIX	31

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Cytomegalovirus incidence

Human Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) or human herpes virus 5 (HHV-5) belongs to the *Herpesviridae* family, subfamily *Betaherpesviridae*, genus *Cytomegalovirus*. It is the largest virus able to infect humans isolated for the first time in 1956¹. HCMV infection is highly prevalent worldwide, mainly in developing countries where almost 100% of the population is infected, compared to 60% in developed countries². The infection is usually asymptomatic in immunocompetent individuals or produces mild symptoms similar to those caused by mononucleosis¹. However, in immunocompromised individuals such as organ transplant recipients and HIV infected patients, HCMV infection can be associated with severe symptoms causing high morbidity and mortality⁴. HCMV transmission occurs through mucous membrane contact or parenterally and can lead to a systemic infection as causing organ diseases such as encephalitis, retinitis, hepatitis, nephritis, splenomegaly, pneumonia and colitis. In addition, HCMV is an important cause of congenital infections worldwide^{5,6}. Transmission of the virus to the fetus/child via transplacental, cervical or vaginal secretions and perinatal infection through breast milk, produces significant sequelae's such as hearing loss and cognitive deficit¹.

CMV is an ubiquitous virus that infects almost all humans at some point during their lives and it is known as the most common congenital viral infection in humans^{6,7}. The incidence of HCMV infection is related to socio-economic factors with a higher incidence in developing countries than in developed countries (Europe and USA) and can affect 100% of the population^{2,5}. In developed countries HCMV infection occurs in two periods during life: during the first 2–3 years of life (associated to maternal transmission) and during the adolescence and early adult life, as a result of sexual contacts¹.

1.2. Cytomegalovirus structure

The HCMV genome consists of a double-stranded DNA with 235Kbp coding for more than 200 open reading frames¹. The genome is located inside the icosahedral nucleocapsid that is surrounded by a protein tegument¹ and the viral envelope that is acquired from the membrane of the infected cells that contains both viral and cell embedded proteins⁸. The structure of the HCMV genome is formed by a unique long (U_L) and short (U_S) regions separated by internal repeat regions (IRL, IRS) and ended by terminal repeats (TRL, TRS) that allow the viral genome to exist as different isomers⁹. Protein expression occurs in 3-phases².

First, the α or IE ("immediate early") genes are expressed engaging the virus to lytic replication. The IE proteins modulate the host cell environment and stimulate the expression of viral early genes (E) which express β proteins. Early proteins are mostly involved in DNA replication. After DNA replication, late viral (L) γ proteins are expressed that are structural proteins involved in the formation of the virion such as the envelope glycoproteins (gp), that are target of neutralizing antibodies, the capsid proteins and the tegument proteins².

1.3. Cytomegalovirus infection and disease

HCMV has a broad cell tropism (fibroblasts, epithelial cells of gland and mucosal tissue, smooth muscle cells, macrophages, neutrophils, dendritic cells, hepatocytes, and vascular endothelial cells) being the epithelial cells the main target during natural infection^{10,11}. This wide cell tropism facilitates the systemic spread and the transmission between different hosts. HCMV has a long cell cycle taking up to 21 days to produce viral progeny in culture¹². After primary infection, HCMV can establish long-life latency in myeloid cells of the host that is characterized by a decreased viral expression with a very small number of viral transcripts with sporadic reactivations⁴. Periodic reactivations arise as productive lytic infections that can cause disease and allow viral spread¹³.

1.3.1. Cell cycle

During HCMV infection, different entry mechanisms are used based on the infected cell and the viral envelope proteins and cell receptors involved¹⁴. The envelope glycoproteins interact with cell receptors to mediate fusion or endocytosis of the virion into the cells⁴. During entry, the viral envelope can fuse with the cell membrane through a pH independent process, and as a result viral capsids are released into the cytoplasm. In the case of viral entry through endocytosis, the virion evaginates into a vesicle and the increase in pH causes the fusion of the membranes (virus envelope and the vesicle membrane), releasing the capsid into the cytoplasm. Once in the cytoplasm, the capsid migrates to the nuclear membrane and the genome is released and circularized into the nucleus⁴ where the viral genome is replicated. The transcripts are transported to the cytoplasm where are translated to proteins that will return to the nucleus to assemble the viral particles. The assembled capsids cross the nuclear membrane to reach the cytoplasm using multiple cellular trafficking pathways⁹. A cytoplasmatic assembly complex is formed, and capsids acquire the tegument and the viral envelope from intracellular vesicles. Finally, the generated enveloped infectious particles are released along with non-infectious particles such as dense bodies^{4,15,16}.

1.3.2. Cell infection

During infection, CMV uses different entry mechanisms depending on the type of cell infected^{17,18}. The initial attachment of CMV to the cell is mediated for all type of cells by the interaction between gM/gN and glycosaminoglycans on the cell membrane^{19,20}. After initial recognition in fibroblasts entry takes places through the interaction between gH/gL/gO and the cellular receptors followed by a pH-independent fusion of the virion envelope mediated by gB and gH/gL/gO with the cellular membrane¹¹. In epithelial cells, entry occurs mainly through the interaction between the pentameric complex and the cell receptors, triggering pentameric complex-mediated endocytosis²¹. Recently it has been shown that entry can occur in both type of cells using a macropinocytosis-like pathway¹⁴ (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of HCMV entry into fibroblast and epithelial cells. Figure adapted from A. Vanarsdall et al (2012)²¹.

1.4. Treatment of cytomegalovirus infection

Based on the severity caused by HCMV infection in immunocompromised individuals efforts have been made for developing a vaccine against HCMV. Although several vaccine candidates (based on recombinant proteins, attenuated viruses and DNA, among others) have been characterized in experimental models and clinical trials over the last 40 years, no vaccine has yet been approved for clinical use²².

Antiviral drugs to treat CMV infection have really improved during the years and treatment of CMV infection has been widely developed in transplant recipients²³. Antivirals such as ganciclovir (GCV), acyclovir (ACV), valganciclovir (VGC) and valacyclovir (VCV) are used as universal prophylaxis, starting within 10 days after transplant and continuing for 3-6 months or as a preemptive treatment guided by viral load results²⁴. As the second line of treatment, cidofovir (CDV), foscarnet (FOS) are used in cases of toxicity or selection of resistance mutations, while letermovir (LVM) is approved as compassionate treatment.

The mechanism of action of the main antivirals used for treatment are shown in Figure 2. The target of GCV, FOS and CDV is the viral DNA polymerase (UL54). Both GCV and CDV need to undergo initial phosphorylation either by viral or cellular kinases in order to be active. GCV is a guanosine analogue lacking ribose that is phosphorylated by the UL97 viral kinase and then converted by the cellular kinases to a triphosphate that inhibits the viral DNA polymerase²⁵. CDV is a phosphonmethoxy analogue of cytosine that acts as a competitive inhibitor of the viral DNA polymerase. Unlike GCV, CDV does not require initial phosphorylation by viral kinases and it only needs to be dephosphorylated by cellular kinases²⁶. In contrast, FOS is a competitive inhibitor and a pyrophosphate analogue that binds to the pyrophosphate binding site of the viral DNA polymerase²⁷. Since they share the same target, cross-resistance is very common²⁸. Letermovir acts at viral DNA cleavage and encapsidation (UL56) affecting the formation of genome units of appropriate length and interferes with virion maturation²⁹. Lastly, maribavir (MBV) inhibits nuclear egress of release formed CMV virions by inhibiting the viral kinase UL97³⁰.

Although these antivirals are highly effective, they are associated with side effects such as nephrotoxicity and high costs³¹ in addition to the selection of resistance mutations. Thus, strong efforts have been made to search for new therapeutic approaches²⁴.

Figure 2. Mechanism of action of the main antivirals used for HCMV infection. GCV and CDV require initial phosphorylation. After being phosphorylated, they compete with dNTPs for the binding site on the viral DNA polymerase thereby inhibiting viral DNA replication. FOS directly inhibits viral DNA replication by blocking the pyrophosphate (ppi) binding site. MP: monophosphate; DP: diphosphate; TP: triphosphate.

1.5. Biological activity of essential oils

Essential oils (EOs) are volatile, natural, liquid and complex mixtures of low-molecular-weight compounds biosynthesized by mostly leaves and nonwoody parts of certain plant families, e.g., *Alliaceae*, *Apiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Brassicaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Myrtaceae*, and *Rutaceae*³². Extracted EOs possess aromatic-smelling compounds including monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes hydrocarbons, phenols, oxides, esters, aldehydes, and ketones as well as different phenylpropene derivatives. They are formed as secondary metabolites in response to attacks by insects, herbivores, and other organisms³³. EOs have been traditionally used as flavouring agents in food products and perfume preparations³⁴ however, they also have significant medicinal properties used either alone or in combination. The presence of different compounds in the oil facilitate its use as antimicrobial agents, representing a natural alternative against multidrug resistant pathogens³³. Some EOs like Eugenol³⁵, thymol³⁶ and vanillin³⁷ have known antimicrobial properties. Previous studies using EOs or their constituents have shown antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria and yeasts, disrupting the cell membrane

leading to cell death³⁸. Recent studies have also shown that several EOs and their major components specifically monoterpenes³⁹, exhibit antiviral activity against enveloped viruses. However, no studies have been applied to HCMV infection.

Despite the described antimicrobial properties of some EOs, some limitations such as strong high volatility, strong sensory properties, poor water solubility or degradability have been found in direct application, e.g. in the food industry. Hence, research has focused on the development of new inorganic materials as porous siliceous supports to graft different antimicrobials⁴⁰.

1.5.1. Eugenol

Eugenol is a phenolic derivative (Figure 3) obtained from some plants mainly *Syzygium aromaticum*. Due to its potent activity against oral anaerobic bacteria, eugenol has been used in dental practice for centuries⁴¹. Since anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties have also been described, eugenol has been also applied as a food preservative and in personal healthcare products and it was listed as a “Generally Regarded As Safe” (GRAS) chemical by the US Food and Drug Administration⁴².

Figure 3. Structural formula of eugenol molecule

1.5.2. Thymol

Thymol is one of the major essential oil constituent of the medicinal plant thyme (*Thymus vulgaris* L., Lamiaceae). Thymol is an isomer of carvacrol and it is a natural phenol monoterpene (Figure 4) currently used in the treatment of respiratory tract diseases, and it has also previously been used to treat digestive, cardiovascular and nervous systems disorders⁴³.

Figure 4. Structural formula of thymol molecule

1.5.3. Vanillin

Vanillin is a phenolic molecule (Figure 5) and is the major constituent of vanilla beans of some plants of the genus *Vanilla*³⁷. Vanillin has been mainly used in foods and fragrance industries and it is one of the most important flavouring agents used in a wide range of products due to its GRAS status⁴⁴.

Figure 5. Structural formula of vanillin molecule

1.6. Enhanced essential oils in surface of silica supports

Currently, the encapsulation or immobilisation of bioactive molecules in nano- and microparticles of silica as an inorganic support, has attracted great interest⁴⁵ due to the increase in antimicrobial activity of the EOCs when they are attached to the support. It has been shown that the treatment of certain microorganisms with EOCs-functionalized particles significantly reduced the growth capacity and viability of the target microorganisms⁴⁶. Ruiz-Rico et al., (2017)⁴⁰ demonstrated the antimicrobial effect against *L. innocua* and *E. coli* of different EOCs-functionalized supports was improved compared to free compounds. In a later comparative cytotoxic study in HepG2 cells, vanillin and eugenol had a milder cytotoxic effect than the equal concentrations of immobilised components on different silica particles⁴⁷. These methodologies of encapsulation or immobilisation of the active compound on the surface of

the silica particle is an attractive option for the design of new antimicrobial formulations that may find applications in different fields other than food industry⁴⁵. Furthermore, previous works have demonstrated that weak binding affinity with a surface and the stability of an enzyme or a protein conjugate is enhanced by immobilization on the surface of nanomaterials⁴⁸. These natural modified nanoparticles offer a new approach for the design of new antimicrobials, since in many cases can potentiate the antimicrobial activity⁴⁹ and reduce the potential toxicity of the assayed compounds⁵⁰.

2. OBJECTIVES

In summary, new therapeutic options are needed for HCMV infection especially for immunocompromised individuals, as an alternative to solve the associated side effects and cross-resistance of the currently available drugs.

Thus, the main aim of this work was to identify new natural compounds with antiviral activity against HCMV as a therapeutic alternative to current treatments. To fulfil this main goal, the following specific objectives have been set:

1. Determine and compare the cytotoxicity of eugenol, thymol and vanillin, both free and functionalized on silica particles, using two different human cell targets (fibroblasts-MRC-5 and epithelium-ARPE-19).
2. Evaluate the in vitro antiviral activity of these three compounds against HCMV infection of human cells in culture.
3. Characterize the potential viral protein target of the compound antiviral activity using transcriptional analysis.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Cells and virus

MRC-5 (ATCC: CCL-171) cell line are lung tissue derived fibroblasts from and ARPE-19 (ATCC: CRL-2302) cell line are retinal pigment derived epithelia cells that were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC; Manassas, VA). Both cells were grown in monolayers in 75-cm² (T-75) cell culture flask using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 10 units of Penicillin, 10 µg Streptomycin and 20 mM glutamine (Lonza), at 37°C and 5% CO₂. For the assays, 15.000 MRC-5 cells and 30.000 ARPE-19 cells were plated in 96-well plates for cytotoxic analysis and for antiviral activity assays (that used 96-well Black/Clear Bottom Plate). To study target gene expression levels, RNA extractions were performed using 6-well plates were used with either 450.000 MRC-5 and 600.000 ARPE-19 infected cells. A laboratory GFP-CMV AD169 strain, provided by Dr. Shenk (Princeton University), was used and propagated on MRC-5 cells in 175-cm² (T-175) cell culture flasks until reaching 85-90% confluency.

3.2. EOCs handling

The synthesis of free EOCs and the functionalization based on anchoring to the surface of silica particles was carried out at the Polytechnic University of Valencia. Bare and functionalized particles were previously characterized to determine their size, surface charge, content of organic matter of the solids and degree of functionalization (39).

3.2.1. Free EOCs

Stock solutions of essential oils were prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) 100% and due to the toxicity of the DMSO in cells, the compounds were used in cell assays at a concentration of DMSO ≤ 0.1%. The concentration range used in the cytotoxicity analysis were from 0 to 14,8 mM for eugenol and from 0 to 10 mM for thymol and vanillin. However, to determine the antiviral activity of the compounds, it was determined which concentrations exhibited no toxicity for the cells. Values were chosen based on the cell viability results.

3.2.2. Silica particles functionalized with EOC preparation

The synthesis of silica particles and their functionalisation with EOCs was carried out at the Polytechnic University of Valencia. As well, the characterisation of bare and functionalized particles has been performed by usual techniques such as particle size distribution,

morphological analysis, determination of the degree of functionalization and zeta potential. The number of particles per gram of solid was calculated according to the data acquired from the characterization techniques.

Unlike with free EOCs, bare and functionalized silica particles were suspended in DMEM. Taking into account the content of organic matter of the solids (Table 1), the corresponding amount of solid in order to have the desired concentration of immobilised EOCs was weight for the cytotoxicity assay (0.05-4 mM). The ranges of concentrations tested for the antiviral activity assay for the particles were different. In order to disperse the particles, particles' suspensions were sonicated for 5 min before each experiment.

Table 1. Content (α) in grams of EOCs per gram of SiO₂ for amorphous silica (AS) particles

Amorphous silica (AS) particles (g/g SiO ₂)	
α_{eugenol}	0.093
α_{thymol}	0.059
α_{vanillin}	0.087

3.3. Cytotoxicity assay

In order to elucidate the toxic effects on cells of the free and functionalized EOCs, we carried out AlamarBlue assay to determine cell viability. AlamarBlue is a redox assay, non-fluorescence blue resazurin is reduced by metabolically active cells, to a fluorescence pink resorufin due to the cellular reducing environment (Figure 6). Resazurin can be reduced by all the components of the cellular respiration metabolic reactions and several enzymes found in the cytoplasm and mitochondria (e.g. reductases and diaphorases). In addition, the conversion of resazurin to resorufin can be detected using absorbance-based plate readers.

Figure 6. Reaction of AlamarBlue assay

After growing cells on 96-well culture plates for 24h, the medium was replaced with media containing the different concentrations of the free and functionalized tested compounds. Plates were incubated for 24h at 37°C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere, after which the AlamarBlue assay was carried out. First, cells were washed once with PBS 1X and a mixture of 90 µL DMEM and 10µL AlamarBlue reagent was added to each well. Subsequently, plates were incubated at 37°C for 4 hours and the absorbance was measured at 570-600 nm. Non-viable or damaged cells were expected to have lower signal than healthy viable cells due to lower metabolic activity. The inhibitory effect of each compound was evaluated compared to either cells with DMEM + 0.1% DMSO in free EOCs and cells with DMEM in functionalized silica particles used as controls. Toxic concentration value (TC₅₀) for each compound was calculated when possible using sigmoidal dose-response curves using GraphPad Prism software (GraphPad Software, USA).

3.4. Antiviral activity assay

In order to determine the antiviral activity of eugenol, thymol and vanillin, HCMV infection inhibition assays were carried out. The concentrations in which the viability was above 80% were selected as therapeutic concentrations. Cells were grown in a 96-well Black/Clear Bottom Plate during 24h. The next day, GFP-CMV strain at a 0.5 multiplicity of infection (MOI) was mixed with increasing concentrations of the free and functional compounds and were incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. After this time, the mixtures were added to the previously cultured cells and were incubated for 48h at 37°C. As a 100% infection control for the experiments with free compounds, untreated infected cells in DMEM medium + 0.1% DMSO were used. For the experiments with bare and functionalized silica particles, DMSO was not added to positive control infected cells.

3.5. Fluorescence microscopy analysis

The analysis of the GFP expressing infected cells was performed using fluorescence microscopy (Cytell). In order to do that, cells were fixed with 1% paraformaldehyde for 10 minutes at RT and nuclei were stained with 5 µg/mL of Hoechst for 30 minutes at room temperature. Figure 7 shows a schematic of the methodology used. The percentage of infected cells (green-GFP signal) was calculated based on the total number of cells stained with the Hoechst nucleus marker (blue). The software Cytell™ Cell Imaging System (v3.6.7.19) was used for the analysis. For each well, 6 images were taken with the 10X objective to homogeneously cover the whole surface of the well (Figure 7). The percentages of infection were obtained, and the inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values were calculated using sigmoidal dose response curves

(GraphPad Software). The selective index (SI) of each compound was also calculated dividing the TC_{50} by the IC_{50} . The compound with the highest selectivity index will be the one of interest.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the methodology for the identification and analysis of potential antiviral candidates using fluorescence microscopy (Cytell)

3.6. RNA extraction and qPCR

Plates were incubated for 2h at 37°C in the presence of the compounds. After this time, virus was added at a 0.5 MOI= followed by 48h incubation at 37°C. Then, cells were collected and centrifuged at 4000 rpm. The cell pellet was frozen at -80°C until further use. RNA from cells were extracted with E.Z.N.A.[®] Total RNA Kit I (Omega Biotek). All extractions were undertaken according to manufacturer's protocol. Eluted RNA samples were stored at -80°C until used. RNA concentration, integrity and purity of the sample respect to protein contamination were measured using the Nanodrop at an OD260/280 ratio.

Subsequently, 1 ng of RNA from each sample was treated for 30 minutes at 37°C with DNAase I (Thermo Scientific, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Maxima Reverse Transcriptase (Thermo Scientific, USA) was used to synthesize cDNA from the DNAase I-treated RNA according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Real-time quantitative PCR was performed on a Light Cycler 480 II (Roche) using the TB Green Premix Ex Taq II (Tli RNase H Plus) (TaKaRa, Japan) for fluorescent labelling. In order to achieve this, 2.5 µl of the cDNA mixture was added to each reaction containing 0.4 µM of the corresponding oligonucleotides (Table 2) and 7.5 µL of the RT-PCR MIX in a final volume of 10 µl. Real-time PCR was performed under the following conditions: 95°C for 10 s, followed by 40 cycles of 10 s at 95°C and 15 s at 55°C. At the end of the amplification cycles, a melting curve analysis was performed to verify the specificity of the reaction. A standard curve was performed with serial dilutions of the cDNA sample (2×10^{-1} , 1×10^{-1} , 2×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-2} , 2×10^{-3} and 1×10^{-3}). GAPDH_{q_F} and GAPDH_R were used to determine GAPDH mRNA levels as an internal control. Data and error bars represent the mean and standard deviations of three independent biological triplicates.

Table 2. Oligonucleotides used in this work for gene amplification

Gene	Forward	Reverse
GAPDH	GGTGTGAACCATGAGAAGTATGA	GAGTCCTCCACGATACCAAAG
UL54	GAGCCTGTATCCGAGCATTATT	CAGGGTCACGCTATACACATC
UL97	ATGTTACCACCCTGCTTTCC	ACAGCTCCGACATGCAATAA
UL56	GGCCGATGAAGAAGAGAATAGG	CAAGCCAGTCCGATGTGAATA
UL51	GGCCTGCTCCTATTACGATAAC	CGGTCCACCATCTTCACATT

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Cell toxicity and antimicrobial activity of the free EOCs

We first performed a cell toxicity study of the EOCs to determine the maximum concentration of the compounds that can be used without affecting cell toxicity and to determine the cell toxicity level that can be assume. Cell toxicity was determined analysing cell viability as described in the method section. The results obtained for ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells are shown in Figure 8 and Table 3. Dose-response curves were obtained representing the percentage of viable cells versus the logarithm of increasing concentration of EOCs (μM). Furthermore, TC_{50} was determined (Table 3) indicating which concentration reduced 50% cell viability.

The potential activity of the compounds was also tested. In this way, in Figure 9, the logarithm of the EOCs concentration versus the HCMV infection is also represented. In this case, the concentration of essential oils that reduced the percentage of infection in 50% (IC_{50}) was also obtained from the dose-response curves (Table 3). Table 3 shows the selectivity index ($\text{SI}=\text{TC}_{50}/\text{IC}_{50}$) for each compound in each of the assayed cell lines. This parameter indicates which compound was less toxic and more antiviral to the cells. The highest selectivity SI values, the better is the antiviral compound.

ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells exposed to eugenol exhibited significant reductions in the cell viability in the range from 325 μM and 1900 μM respectively. Although the curve trend was similar in both cell lines (Figure 8A and 8B), eugenol was slightly more toxic for MRC-5 ($\text{TC}_{50}=0.44$) than for ARPE-19 ($\text{TC}_{50}=1.99$) cells. On the other hand, the IC_{50} for ARPE-19 was 0.32 mM while in MRC-5 was 0.02 mM, i.e., a higher concentration of eugenol in ARPE-19 is needed to reduce the HCMV infection by 50%. These values evidenced a greater antiviral effect on MRC-5

than in ARPE-19 cells. This is also reflected in the SI which had an order of magnitude three times higher in MRC-5. The cytotoxicity and the antiviral activity of eugenol was previously evaluated both *in vitro* and *in vivo* in monkey kidney Vero cells infected with herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) and type 2 (HSV-2)⁵¹. In that study, the IC₅₀ was 0.156 mM and the maximum dose of eugenol at which cytotoxicity was tested (1.52 mM) had not cytotoxic effects, and the SI was not shown. Thus, it is not possible to compare whether eugenol has more antiviral activity in ARPE-19 and MRC-5 versus in Vero cells.

In the case of the cells exposed to thymol, despite having similar kinetics to those obtained with eugenol in the cytotoxicity test, important differences regarding to the TC₅₀ values were revealed. Thymol had lower toxicity effect in both cell types in comparison to eugenol, consequently their TC₅₀ values were higher. Additionally, TC₅₀ values were very similar in both cell lines: 2.35 mM for MRC-5 and 2.15 mM for ARPE-19. Several authors have evidenced non cytotoxic effects in Caco-2 cells at a 250 µM concentration³⁴ and in primary cultures of mouse cortical neurons at a 1000 µM concentration⁵². Considering the obtained IC₅₀ and the SI, thymol was proved to be more antiviral and less toxic in fibroblast (SI=4.70) than in epithelial cells (SI=1.76) highlighting the potential different mechanisms of action and the importance of perform the assays with different cell lines.

On the contrary, cells incubated with vanillin remained almost unaltered with TC₅₀ values of 23442 mM and 8851 mM in ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells, respectively. Among the three EOCs tested, the IC₅₀ value for vanillin was the highest in both cell lines compared with those obtained for eugenol and thymol. Thus, the concentrations used to test the antiviral activity for vanillin were also higher. This fact was also described by Ruiz-Rico et al., (2017)⁴⁰ when analysing the antiviral effect of vanillin on *E. coli* and *L. innocua*. Nonetheless, due to the little toxicity on the cells, vanillin was found to have a considerable antiviral activity with very high selectivity index especially in epithelial cells which are the main target during natural infection (ARPE-19=15123.87; MRC-5=1738.90). In addition, to the strong antiviral potential of vanillin against CMV, its antitumour activity has also been described in the human chronic myeloid leukaemia cell line K562⁵⁰.

Figure 8. Percentage of viability and infection after incubation with eugenol, thymol and vanillin in ARPE-19 (A, B, C) and MRC-5 (D, E, F) cells according to the logarithm of the EOC concentration. DMSO-treated cells were used as controls.

4.2. Cell toxicity and antiviral activity of the EOCs-functionalized and bare silica particles

To assess the antiviral activity of the EOCs immobilised onto the surface of silica particles, cell cytotoxicity was measured after incubating cells in the presence of particles functionalized with EOCs. The possible antiviral effect of the bare silica was also tested to confirm that the antiviral activity only lays on EOCs and it is not due to the support. Figures 9 and 10 show the results of the percentage of viability and infection comparing SiO₂ particles functionalized (A, B and C) and bare (D, E and F) in ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells, respectively.

As in the case of free EOCs, dose-response curves were obtained by representing the percentage of viable cells versus the logarithm of increasing concentration of EOCs (mM). TC₅₀, IC₅₀ and SI parameters are also shown in Table 3.

The addition of the eugenol-functionalized particles resulted in an increased antiviral activity that was higher for ARPE-19 than for MRC-5 cells (Figure 9A and 10A). It is noteworthy that despite obtaining a higher TC₅₀ value in MRC-5 (4.24 mM) than in ARPE-19 (0.15 mM), the selectivity index is better in ARPE-19 (15 mM) due to the highest antiviral activity. This result is very interesting because the epithelium is the first natural target during HCMV infection¹². In ARPE-19 cells thymol particles proved to have a potent antiviral effect (SI= 9287.57) because when viability was almost 100%, infection was reduced to approximately 50% (Figure 10B). In addition, cell viability remained high when the infection percentage was 0 (TC₅₀=650.13 mM). Although in MRC-5 the IC₅₀ was promising (0.20 mM), the viability results were not as good as in the case of ARPE-19 (Figure 10B). Finally, the obtained results in the viability assay for functionalized vanillin were very similar in both ARPE-19 and MRC-5 (Figures 9C and 10C). Vanillin presented low toxicity with TC₅₀ values of 7.18x10¹⁰ mM and 799.83 mM in ARPE-19 and MRC-5, respectively. On the other hand, the trend of the infection curve was different for both cell lines. In ARPE-19, there was an abrupt decrease in infection at a concentration of 0.26 mM comparing with MRC-5 where the reduction of infection was more progressive (Figures 9C and 9C). Nevertheless, as with free EOCs, functionalized vanillin proved to be the best candidate as a potential antiviral agent in both cell lines, with much higher selectivity indexes than those obtained for functionalized thymol and eugenol. This turned out to be interesting because several authors have described its antiviral effect on bacteria^{44,53} but very few on viruses. Moreover, it has to be pointed out that for ARPE-19, addition of the bare silica particles at the corresponding concentrations of each compound resulted in a decrease in the viability (Figures 9D, E, F) while the infection percentages remained almost 100%. This

concentration-dependent reduction of viability has been described by other authors testing different types of particles as carriers to enhance the antimicrobial activity of certain compounds⁴⁷. Curiously, when EOCs were immobilised on silica particles, viability was not as affected, especially in the case of thymol and vanillin, and infection percentages decreased considerably. This was evidenced in the high selectivity index values obtained (Table 3).

In the case of MRC-5 cells, apparently, the addition of bare particles caused a decrease in the infection percentages, mainly in thymol and vanillin (Figure 10E and F). However, this result was actually biased because when the cells were observed under the fluorescence microscope, they were all dead due to bare particle and the infection of the virus (see Appendix, Figure 13). Nonetheless, in spite of this, the antiviral effect was enhanced when the natural compounds were incorporated into the silica particles with very promising SI results. These results also shed light into the importance of perform the analysis in different cell targets.

If we compare the cytotoxic of free and functionalized EOCs in ARPE-19 cells, thymol and vanillin, presented a lower cytotoxic effect in their free form compared to that of immobilised on silica particles' surfaces. This has also been described by Fuentes et al., (2021)⁴⁷ in a study comparing the cytotoxicity of the vanillin-functionalized particles and free vanillin using concentrations of 1.25 and 2.5 mM. In contrast, in MRC-5 cells, eugenol was found to be the most toxic in its free form. This is in line with the study by Chen et al., (2009)⁵⁴ where the cytotoxic effect of chitosan nanoparticles functionalized with eugenol was evaluated. Similarly, the results reported herein, cytotoxicity assays using 3T3 mouse fibroblast showed that eugenol functionalized particles were significantly less cytotoxic than free EOCs. However, significant differences have been found in other studies in the TC_{50} values of eugenol⁴⁷, so depending on the cell type employed the results appear to be different.

Furthermore, the immobilisation of the three EOCs on silica particles has demonstrated to significantly increase their antimicrobial activity against HCMV compared to free EOCs in ARPE-19 cells. This has been previously described against other types of microorganisms using different types of particles as carriers for encapsulation or immobilisation^{45,46}. In contrast, in MRC-5 cells, only the functionalized thymol was found to be better antiviral than when it was free. Ruiz-Rico et al., (2017)⁴⁰ demonstrated that high concentrations (0.50–1,33 mM) of immobilized thymol on certain supports displayed improved antimicrobial activity compared to the free compound.

Figure 9. Percentage of viability and infection after incubation with eugenol, thymol and vanillin functionalized in silica particles and in bare particles in ARPE-19 cells according to the logarithm of the EOC concentration. Cells with DMEM were used as controls.

Figure 10. Percentage of viability and infection after incubation with eugenol, thymol and vanillin functionalized in silica particles and in bare particles in MRC-5 cells according to the logarithm of the EOC concentration. Cells with DMEM were used as controls.

Table 2. IC₅₀, TC₅₀ and Selectivity Index (SI=TC₅₀/IC₅₀) for the tested compounds against HCMV in ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells. Cells were exposed for 2 hours with serial dilutions of each compound and then infected with HCMV in the presence of compounds during 24 h. After fixation, plates were stained; images acquired using a Cytell microscope were quantified to determine percentages of infection. AlamarBlue assays matched the duration of the infection. A “~” symbol indicates that the non-linear regression curve fit was ambiguous, as defined by the GraphPad Prism software. The IC₅₀ and TC₅₀ values derived from at least four independent experiments.

		ARPE-19			MRC-5		
		TC ₅₀ (mM)	IC ₅₀ (mM)	SI (mM)	TC ₅₀ (mM)	IC ₅₀ (mM)	SI (mM)
Free EOCs	eugenol	1.99	0.32	6.22	0.44	0.02	22
	thymol	2.15	1.22	1.76	2.35	0.50	4.70
	vanillin	23442	1.55	15123.87	8851	5.09	1738.90
Functionalized silica particles	eugenol	0.15	0.01	15	4.24	0.37	11.46
	thymol	650.13	0.07	9287.57	1.65	0.20	8.25
	vanillin	7.18x10 ¹⁰	0.26	2.76x10 ¹¹	799.83	1.97	406.01
Bare particles	eugenol	1.05	1x10 ¹²⁰	1.05x10 ⁻¹²⁰	42.59	50.70	0.84
	thymol	2.78	~	~	20.17	0.60	33.62
	vanillin	5.51	~	~	3.96	1.13	3.50

TC₅₀, 50% toxic concentration (mM); IC₅₀, 50% inhibitory concentration of HCMV-GFP infection (mM); SI, antiviral selectivity index values (SI= TC50/IC50) (mM).

4.3. Viral transcript expression analysis of the main antiviral genomic targets

Most of the antivirals developed target the same viral proteins⁵⁵, including UL51, UL54, UL56, UL97. These proteins are the most common therapeutic targets because they are essential for viral replication, and there is a strong probability that the compounds with high antiviral activity tested in this study would be also directed against them. Although it would be ideal to find other HCMV antivirals that are directed to different targets to solve the problem of cross-resistance to current drugs⁵⁵.

Since vanillin was the compound with more potent antiviral activity in both cell types and because we did not have additional time to complete the study, vanillin was chosen to further study its effect on viral transcription of the four main targets of the antiviral therapies: UL51, UL54, UL56, UL97. However, thymol and eugenol will be also further evaluated in the near future.

Three concentrations of each compound were selected to cover the full range of the dose-response curves for each condition and tested in both cell lines in triplicate. A schematic representation of the methodologic design is shown in Figure 11. RNA expression levels for the 4 studied genes from infected cells grown in the presence of different concentrations of free vanillin are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Diagram to illustrate the different tested of free vanillin concentrations along the infection curves for ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells.

HCMV-infected ARPE-19 cells treated with vanillin exhibited low levels of UL54 mRNA compared to the control, mainly in the lower concentrations (V1 and V2). This also happened for the UL97, UL56 and UL51 genes in ARPE-19 cells. However, in MRC-5 cells, UL56 seemed to be the only gene with decreased expression in the presence of vanillin at both high and low concentrations. UL56 is part of the terminase complex that is involved in DNA packaging through sequence-specific binding of DNA packaging motifs in CMV genome concatemers⁵⁶. In contrast, the expression levels of UL54 and UL51 at the highest assayed concentration were higher than those obtained for the control indicating that vanillin does not target viral polymerase, nor does it target one of the terminase complex components in MRC-5 cells. These results are very interesting because vanillin could be used as new therapy by itself or can be added in combination with the current antivirals to produce a synergistic effect. In this case, it could be possible to decrease the concentration of the antiviral that may result in a decrease toxicity and less selection of resistance mutations. In fact, the synergy between eugenol and acyclovir has been already demonstrated in herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) and 2 (HSV-2) infection⁵¹. On the other hand, several works have been carried out to determine the effect of vanillin in different scenarios. Recently it has been described that vanillin could dampen the virulence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by acting on the QS regulator

response⁵⁷. In addition, it has been shown that vanillin might be a potent antiinvasive agent that suppresses the MMP-9 enzymatic activity via NF-kappaB signalling pathway⁵⁸. Again, our data highlight the importance of studying and validating the obtained effects in different cell types. In fact, the comparative study of the different transcriptional regulation could increase our knowledge about the mechanism of action of the tested compounds.

Figure 12. Comparison of the expression levels of UL54, UL97, UL56 and UL51 HCMV genes in both ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells. Cells infected with HCMV (MOI=0.5) were grown in the presence of different concentrations of free vanillin (V1=100, V2=2500 and 5000 μ M for MRC-5 and ARPE-19, respectively and V3=7000 μ M). Expression levels of mRNA were obtained from RT-qPCR normalized with the constitutive gene GAPDH. Dashed line indicates the expression of the control condition. The asterisk (*) indicates significant differences (p-value \leq 0.05) compared with controls (ARPE-19 and MRC-5 in DMEM+0.1% DMSO).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Vanillin, both free and functionalized, proved to be the compound with the highest antiviral potential against HCMV with very high selectivity index in both cell lines, especially in epithelial cells, which are the main natural target during infection. Functionalized thymol was the second best antiviral candidate in ARPE-19 cells. However, among the three tested compounds, thymol (in its free form) was the least effective against infection on both ARPE-19 and MRC-5 cells. In contrast, free eugenol appears to be the most effective in MRC-5, while functionalized eugenol had better antiviral effect on ARPE-19 cells. Although the results differed depending on the particle type, either with bare and EOCs-functionalized particles, all three tested compounds improved their antiviral activity in ARPE-19 cells when attached to silica micro particles.

Our results suggest that vanillin could be explored as a new antiviral that could be used in monotherapy based on the effectivity against infection in human cells in culture. In addition, vanillin could also be used in combination with other current antivirals to produce a synergistic effect allowing to decreasing the antiviral concentration that may result on decreasing toxicity and the selection of resistance mutations.

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APPENDIX

Figure 13. Fluorescent microscopy images of MRC-5. The nucleus of the cells was stained with Hoechst (blue). Panel A and B show nuclei staining and HCMV-GFP infected cells in untreated cells, respectively, and panel C shows staining of nuclei of cells treated with bare-silica particles according to the concentration of thymol 2mM. Panel D and E show the same as A and B, but panel F shows nuclei staining treated with bare-silica particles according to the concentration of vanillin 2mM.

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